

How Path Dependence Shapes Gulf Monarchies' High-Tech Strategies

Andrew Leber

Andrew Leber is an assistant professor at Tulane University's Department of Political Science and Middle East & North Africa (MENA) Studies program. His research focuses on the political economy of authoritarianism, particularly in Saudi Arabia and other Arab Gulf monarchies. His work has appeared in Politics & Society, Democratization, Governance, and the Review of Middle East Studies.

In present policy debates, there is considerable focus on states' AI strategies. The latter are framed as immediate policy choices with the potential to shape countries' long-term economic prospects and, in turn, political ones. Beyond the most advanced AI powers (the United States and China), the monarchies of the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) have attracted attention due to their financial resources, which have allowed them to purchase pricy AI technologies. Furthermore, their fossil-fuel reserves have permitted them to power energy-intensive data centers on the cheap (Winter-Levy 2024; Soliman 2025). Where strategic discussions necessarily focus on the future, historical institutionalist approaches encourage us to understand how path-dependent Gulf development trajectories shape their present AI strategies. Hence, while the "AI revolution" may be a critical juncture (Collier & Collier 1991) that will lock countries into long-term AI divides, state choices concerning the technology are shaped by pre-existing conditions (Slater & Simmons 2010; Soifer 2012).

If the acceleration of AI technologies comprises a critical juncture for countries to invest in transformative technologies, then the near future will test the agency of Gulf states, especially Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates. The question is whether they

will be able to secure the status of AI middle powers against the constraints of past investments in state-owned enterprises, power grids, and human resources (Winter-Levy & Leicht 2026). A common assumption is that the resource wealth of the Gulf monarchies, coupled with a lack of institutional constraints on their leadership, positions them well in the global AI race (Al Soliman 2024; Arafah 2025). Kuwaiti analyst Abdullah AlZabin (2024) dubbed this moment the bloc's "petrocompute" opportunity: "building high-performance compute infrastructure of unprecedented scale to serve the world's rapidly growing demand for A.I." Even in this advantaged position, however, there is a range of potential outcomes for the Gulf states (assuming AI truly proves to be a world-changing technology, and the present war on Iran does not undermine the Gulf's case for hosting AI facilities).

The first trajectory is simply "adaptation" or keeping pace with new developments. It would entail incorporating new AI technologies into state bureaucracies, both service-oriented and repressive ones. It would also involve investing in training and education programs to allow citizens to adapt to changing labor markets. The second approach, known as "stakeholder," is one in which the Gulf states become meaningful

financial stakeholders in tech firms primarily based in the United States, Europe, and possibly China. They would diversify an existing portfolio of economic ties with important security patrons and partners. A third possibility, called “subsidizing,” entails foreign firms, most likely from the United States, incentivizing Gulf states to subsidize the construction of key facilities and promise the provision of cheap electricity thereafter. In the process, these states would integrate themselves into U.S. data flows, generate additional value from hydrocarbon extraction in the form of petrochemical investments, and offer cheap access for local startups to AI inferencing or computer calculations that respond to user queries. Finally, the maximal “petrocompute” outcome is one in which Gulf states go beyond subsidizing foreign inferencing to introduce globally competitive proprietary applications of their own and even train their own AI models, which is far more technically demanding.

While GCC states might prefer an “all of the above” approach, even attempting a higher-payoff strategy requires resources beyond the means of the less wealthy states. Oman and Bahrain, though wealthier in per capita terms than much of the MENA region, are each hard-pressed to maintain their citizens’ existing standards of living while managing debt levels. Accordingly, their AI strategies revolve around adaptation: adopting AI enhancements for “e-government” services and training new job seekers to work with such technologies (Albous et al. 2025: 2400). Furthermore, capturing value from AI is not merely about having cash on hand, but rather the ability or capacity to deliver infrastructure for electricity and data centers, as well as to direct projects through local or locally embedded individuals and institutions. Gulf states have different capacities to invest in projects, deliver electricity, and manage large commercial projects – all of which inform these states’ ultimate AI strategies and

Figure 1. Path dependence and divergent outcomes of Gulf AI investments. Modeled after Slater & Simmons (2010: 894).

trajectories. Resource wealth is part of the equation, but not everything.

Kuwait exemplifies this path dependency. While Kuwait is one of the wealthiest per capita GCC states, it has relatively little recent experience with building state-owned enterprises or boosting private-sector entities to compete regionally, let alone internationally (Herb 2014). This means there are few organizational foundations for building a new AI national champion, and limited non-AI data centers, even relative to Bahrain and Oman. In terms of the human capital to staff such a venture, the Kuwaiti education system struggles to meet existing labor market demands (Alhashem & Alhouti 2021). Furthermore, Kuwaiti officials have focused more on stripping away citizenship rather than attracting skilled expatriate workers (Alamer 2025). Despite some AI-focused efforts by some states and state-owned entities, even limited partnerships with U.S. firms are threatened by underinvestment in the country's power grid – making it hard to turn energy resources into the stuff of petrocompute (Crowley 2026). Accordingly, the bulk of Kuwaiti AI investments reflects a stakeholder strategy, focused on U.S. firms operating in the United States. The Kuwait Investment Authority, for example, has joined U.S. firms and an Emirati tech fund as part of an AI infrastructure partnership.

By contrast, the United Arab Emirates clearly has the greatest AI ambitions among the GCC monarchies, with state-owned firm G42 trying to position itself as the equal of hyperscalers like Microsoft or OpenAI. Along with a general experience in building up successful state-owned enterprises, the UAE benefits from an early intervention in the AI space by Tahnoun bin Zayed – a powerful royal with a longstanding and idiosyncratic interest in

advanced technologies. In 2018, Tahnoun founded G42 by incorporating past UAE-based expertise in cybersecurity and digital surveillance and by pushing to establish the new AI-focused Mohammed bin Zayed University for Artificial Intelligence (Hope 2025; Zhou 2025). G42 is the only Gulf AI firm that has secured major inward investments from a U.S. hyperscaler (Microsoft), beyond deals that channel capital outward towards U.S.-based facilities and companies (Allen et al. 2025). As for staffing these ventures, the UAE, and especially Abu Dhabi, has long been a regional hub for skilled talent of all kinds, with consultants who commute to Saudi Arabia to work on various mega-projects there. Furthermore, while the UAE still faces electrical-capacity challenges, past investments in renewables and the Gulf's only nuclear power plants provide a sounder footing for expanding the grid.

Saudi Arabia, in turn, forms an interesting intermediate case. Its trajectories will offer a clearer indication of the relative importance of sheer wealth and ambition, on the one hand, and past institutional and human resource endowments on the other. Saudi Arabia has sought to match the UAE with its own AI national champion called Humain, its own locally based partnerships with U.S. hyperscaler Groq, and its own supply of top-line U.S. microchips, with the Trump administration releasing equal numbers of Nvidia's latest Blackwell chips (Satoriano & Mozur 2025). Despite new industrialization efforts as part of Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030, Humain's domestic capacity to manage AI projects relies heavily on past investments by national oil company Saudi Aramco – a developmental “island of excellence” (Hertog 2010). Electricity generation is likewise a mixed bag, as Saudi Arabia tries to simultaneously increase output and eliminate inefficient oil-fired

power plants while benefiting from a capable, locally based power-generation firm called ACWA Power. The Kingdom also lacks a deep pool of domestic or expatriate talent, though existing educational institutions are being repurposed to support AI research, and the easing of longstanding social restrictions has made cities like Riyadh more livable in the eyes of many expatriates.

This contribution argues that AI strategies in the Gulf states (and other countries) reflect pre-existing policies, capacities, and constraints. Simply adapting to the economic changes wrought by AI is a daunting challenge; going beyond this to capture value from AI supply chains will depend on Gulf states' past investments in basic infrastructure (electricity provision) and education (citizen labor supply), as well as policies towards migration and business regulation. Costly AI strategies that do not reckon with these constraints are more likely to enrich Western firms and consultants than to diversify Gulf economies. In all, despite the transformative potential of the AI revolution for both economic outcomes and research practices, political scientists should still draw on longstanding historical-institutionalist tools and concepts to explain divergent AI strategies and trajectories across the region. ♦

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